

Condensation of Diphenylmethane with Aldehydes

Vishnu Chandra and Vijay Bahadur Srivastava

Diphenylmethane has been condensed with 5-bromo- and 3:5-dibromosalicylaldehydes in presence of piperidine. Maximum yields obtained were 47.0% and 66.6% respectively. No condensation occurred with benzaldehyde, anisaldehyde, *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde and *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde.

Seiichi Ishikawa *et. al.*,¹ reported that methylene hydrogens in diphenylmethane were not at all acidic. The present investigation has, however, shown that this does not appear to be completely true because diphenylmethane has been condensed with some aldehydes, e.g., bromosalicylaldehydes, although it has been found to be much less reactive than malonic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of 5-bromo- and 3:5-dibromosalicylaldehydes. These were prepared as reported earlier.²

Condensation with 5-bromo salicylaldehyde: Equimolecular amounts of diphenylmethane (0.64 gm.) and aldehyde (0.48 gm.) were heated in 50 c.c. R.B. flask under reflux at different temperatures viz., 100, 120, 140, 160 and 180° for different durations of time viz., 6, 12 and 18 hrs., in the presence of traces of different bases viz., pyridine, piperidine, α -picoline, mixture of pyridine and acetic anhydride, mixture of triethylamine and acetic anhydride and mixture of pyridine and piperidine. The condensed product, so obtained, was washed with ether and the residue left was recrystallised from acetone and water (2 : 1) and was found to be α - α -diphenyl- β -1-(2-hydroxy-5-bromophenyl)-ethylene, m.p., 120-22°. (Found C, 67.5%; H, 4.40%. Br, 22.4%. $C_{20}H_{15}BrO$ requires C, 68.0%; H, 4.28%; Br, 22.7%). Maximum yield of 47.0% of condensed product was obtained when the reactants were heated at 140° for 12 hr. in presence of traces of piperidine.

Condensation with 3:5-dibromo-salicylaldehyde: The product was found to be α : α -(diphenyl)- β -1-(2-hydroxy-3:5-dibromophenyl)-ethylene, m.p.; 128°. (Found C, 55.68%; H, 3.82%. $C_{20}H_{14}Br_2O$ requires C, 55.7%; H, 3.39. Maximum yield of 66.6% was obtained when the reactants were heated at 140° for 12 hr. in presence of traces of piperidine.

DISCUSSION

An attempt was made to condense benzaldehyde, anisaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde and 3:5-dibromosalicylaldehyde with diphenylmethane. Only 5-bromosalicylaldehyde and 3:5-dibromosalicylaldehyde reacted to give 47.0% and 66.6% yields respectively of the

1. Seiichi Ishikawa *et. al.*, *Science Repts. Tokyo Bunrika Diagake.*, 1934, 1, 289.

2. Vishnu Chandra and Srivastava, *This Journal*, 1966, 43, 796.

condensed product. No condensation took place with rest of the aldehydes. Maximum yields in the condensation of malonic acid with the above aldehydes have been reported to be almost quantitative³. The percentage yields in the condensation of phenylacetic acid and above aldehydes have been reported to be 63.3⁴, 68.5⁴, 63.0⁴, 55.4⁵, 28.6⁶, 94.9⁵, 99.9⁶ respectively. It is, therefore, evident that diphenylmethane is much less reactive than malonic and phenylacetic acids. It was found that when diphenylmethane was heated with benzaldehyde, anisaldehyde, *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde, *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde in presence of bases, the aldehydes were oxidised to the corresponding acids and no condensation took place. With *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, a very hard glass attacking resin which was insoluble in all the common solvents, was obtained.

Thanks of the authors are due to Prof. R. P. Rastogi, Head, Chemistry Department, University of Gorakhpur, for providing necessary facilities.

ORGANIC LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY OF GORAKHPUR,
GORAKHPUR. (U.P.)

Received, December 7, 1967.

3. Pandya *et al.*, *This Journal*, 1952, **29**, 363.
4. R. N. Singh *et al.*, *Agra Univ. J. of Res. Science*, 1952, **1**, 153.
5. Buckless *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951 **73**, 4972.
6. Vishnu Chandra and Srivastava, *This Journal*, 1967, **44**, 675.